

Inheritance and Bring Into Play “Ngu Binh U Nong” In Strengthening the People Armed Force Intergrated the Current Economic Development with National Defense

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ABSTRACT: The integration of national defense with economic growth and vice versa that our army has been executing is a legacy of the Ly – Tran – post Le era and brings into action “Ngu binh u nong” (Sending the army into agricultural activities). This policy is a technique of developing an armed force to protect the country, closely merging "army" with "agricultural," economics with defense, constructing and defending the country, assuring national defense strength, and the capacity to rapidly transition from peacetime to warfare to combat foreign invaders. Based on the analysis of historic records on the policy of "Ngu binh u nong," this research examined the features of the organizational art and building up of our forefathers' armed forces throughout our country's history. This is a prominent feature in the creative organization and building of our forefathers' military forces in the growth history of the Vietnamese country. This study also demonstrates the transmission of fundamental values in military art from past generations, and certain experiences in armed force development are obtained as a result of these research findings. It is now referred to as a "whole-population armed army."

KEYWORDS: Sending Army Into Agriculture, Economic, The Policy, National Defense, Armed Force.

I. INTRODUCTION

The history of Vietnam is a narrative of struggle to establish and preserve a country. Over thousands of years, our predecessors were constantly confronted with many foreign invasions, which left an indelible impact on the art of protecting the homeland, in the integration of creating and defending the nation. Dai Viet was known as a prosperous Asian country during the Ly, Tran, and post-Le eras. Based on the findings of domestic and international academics. This was the most prosperous period of growth in the Vietnam feudatory, which was regarded as an era of Vietnamese civilisation. It all started in 1010, when Ly Cong Uan made the unforgettable decision to relocate the capital city from Hoa Lu to Thang Long (known as Hanoi today). (today is Hanoi). After that, Dai Viet put up the most valiant invasion defense. That was the struggle against the Tong Dynasty (1075 – 1077), three times defeating the Mong – Nguyen invasion (in 1258, 1285, and 1288), and ten years revolting against the Minh invasion, liberating the nation under the leadership of Le Loi – Nguyen Trai. In this situation, the dynasties prioritized the building of a strong national defense background capable of swiftly transitioning from peacetime to warfare in order to defend the country against foreign invasion.

A lot of academics have noted the history of the “ngu nong u binh” policy. However, research into this policy as a strategy for growing and retaining the country in compared to the construction of military forces to integrate our economy with national security is still restricted at the moment. As a result, in this research, the author will go into detail about the defense methods used by our forefathers throughout the feudal dynasties of Ly - Tran Le, as well as the experiences encountered during the consolidation process. The Vietnamese army's current all-population defense stance. As a result of the situation, the task of constructing an all-people national defense, constructing people's armed forces in our country during the current revolutionary period, and inheriting the core values in military art from previous generations. In each revolutionary period, our Party has established the proper guidelines and decisions in order to maximize the strength of the all-people defense posture, the people's security posture, and the ability to protect the people, the Party, and the socialist government in the new situation.

The authors of this paper highlight the approach of integrating economy with national security in the history of Dai Viet feudal state country for development and defense. Simultaneously, they emphasize significant experience in constructing an all-people armed force today.

Inheritance and Bring Into Play “Ngu Binh U Nong” In Strengthening the People Armed Force Intergrated the Current Economic Development with National Defense

II. METHODOLOGY

This study relied heavily on historical and dialectical materialist approaches. This research technique was utilized to examine chronological documentation of historical events connected to the defense policy of previous feudal regimes. Using this research approach, the authors authentically investigated and assessed historical events.

The procedures of logical analysis, comparison, and inductive synthesis were also used. The logical technique was utilized to sort and separate historical events based on the timestamps connected with the events under consideration. The approach of analysis and comparison was utilized in comparing historical events from the Ly - Tran - Le dynasties to our Party's present defense policy. To convey study findings in the direction of synthesizing and interpreting events, the inductive and interpretive technique was utilized.

III. A REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

3.1. The “Ngu binh u nong” policy, which combined economic growth with national security in the process of developing and protecting a country.

The historical reality of our nation's struggle to build and defend the country from the 10th to the 15th century shows that under the growing feudal dynasties, there was an invincible strength in the defense of the country: the fighting strength of the nation, with the core being a powerful armed force, including a strong standing force and an extensive rear force.; combined strength of all aspects, including great material potential (manifested in high salary, strong army). One of the great experiences of our ancestors in these periods was to create an invincible power for the defense of the country through the policy of “Ngu binh u nong”– a method of building armed forces to defend the country, closely combining "soldiers" with "farmers", economy with national defense, building and defending the country. This was the strategic policy chosen by all three dynasties, Ly, Tran, and Le So, and it resulted in the maximum efficiency.

Since the Ly dynasty, our country's military regime has been clearly shaped, in which the policy of " Ngu binh u nong " has been built and put into practice. Accordingly, the combination of national defense with economics applied in the standing army organization itself, is regulated into the rules of law. In the book of Dai Viet history, in the entry about the reign of King Le Thanh Tong, the author writes: "Military war in the early Ly dynasty... taking the King's relative as the main importance, also called the forbidden army... In addition, there are 9 troops, like the route army, to command to do everything, once a month it is called to come to guard, after the end of the guard, let them go home to cultivate, do self employment, do not receive a salary. When conquering, they will be called out to depend on the generals." [1]. Accordingly, the forbidden army is a standing force that must be on duty regularly to guard and practice. This type of army is provided and nurtured by the State according to the regime of each period. They were given military equipment and a salary in cash, in rice, and with some other food. As for the other troops, namely "Suong Quan" and "Foreign troops", they are allowed to "take the turn" based on the policy of " Ngu binh u nong ". Units are divided into several sessions; Periodically change each other, one session is on duty in the army, training, guarding or serving, other sessions return to the family to participate in production, self-sufficient food. The book "Vietnamese history of execution" states that: "In the regime of soldiers under the Ly dynasty, farmers were promoted to the army once a month, called guard duty, then returned to work in the fields after the end of the war, the army did not have to pay wages..., which has the effect of using soldiers' power, it is also a good policy." [2]. The strategy of " Ngu binh u nong " vividly proved the role and power of the Ly army as it proceeded to conquer Champa. Wherever Dai Viet's army went, men and supplies were delivered. As a result, the inhabitants of Dai Viet enjoyed wealth, tranquility, and a thriving social life throughout this time period.

Following the policy of the Ly Dynasty, the policy of "Ngu binh u nong" was progressively accomplished and put into order during the Tran Dynasty. The divisional system that allowed troops to return to work in the fields was maintained. The Tran Dynasty's division of troops to labor in the fields was documented in the book "The Tran Dynasty, following the Ly Dynasty's policy, the soldiers and guards all paid annual stipends, the amount of which is unclear." All soldiers, regardless of religion, labor in the fields to save money." [3]. During peacetime, soldiers took turns joining the army, and soldiers took turns farming. The court had a "restrained guard" army, and a "self-defense" force was a mobile standing force with a small number of elites who were picked and trained. There are "foreign troops" and "army soldiers" in the area, who alternately produce self-sufficient food. As a result, the court significantly lowered the expense of raising the army while still constructing and organizing formidable forces, contributing to the creation of general strength to maintain the nation, defeating invading armies that outnumbered us many times in historical terms at the time. This method of arranging forces has resulted in a broad and advantageous defense posture. Wherever there are people, there are troops, or individuals who have been trained in the military, are listed in the records, and have been recruited into the army during peacetime. During the years when the nation was at peace, many countries across the world faced invasion by the Mong - That invader, and the Tran dynasty actively took care of the organization for military training, ready to battle when a war painting occurred. With such approach, when the enemy breached the border, the armed forces in the region might be mobilized to conduct a timely interception. Especially when dealing with a large-scale invasion war, the court can swiftly organize huge resources and have an abundance of supplementary resources during the resistance battle.

Inheritance and Bring Into Play “Ngu Binh U Nong” In Strengthening the People Armed Force Intergrated the Current Economic Development with National Defense

During the early Le dynasty, the country's military system was likewise altered to accommodate the new political structure. The first level is still the imperial army, the second is the government army, and the third is the army of clan imperialists. The Le dynasty gave great attention to the formation of civil status, personal inventory, and control of a number of domestic branches in order to build up the military forces to protect the nation. During the years of struggle against the Ming invaders, Lam Son insurgent forces grew swiftly, from few to numerous, guerilla to regular, and reached a mature degree of power. When the war ended, the imperial court lowered the number of standing troops and arranged production sessions for the troops, boosted material and technological equipment for the army, and raised the rank of generals.

In summary, the policy of "Ngu binh u nong" with the basic content of conscription for all soldiers and the division of soldiers in production was issued and started to be implemented from the Ly dynasty, continued to be implemented and further strengthened in the Tran and early Le dynasties. This policy was a unique method of building the armed forces to defend the country, an integral part of the national management and defense strategy of the Dai Viet feudal state at that time. The success and unique innovation of the policy of " Ngu binh u nong " at that time was to build a small but elite army, with a large reserve force, well-trained. The more, ready to become the main force to deal with the invasion of foreign forces.

3.2. Mobilizing the entire population to participate in building the armed forces, combining economy with national defense in the revolutionary war

Combining economic development with strengthening national defense potential is an objective indispensable element, an important content in the country development path of our Communist of Party, in order to successfully realize two strategic tasks: building and firmly protecting the Socialist Vietnam Fatherland. The fact of the nation's development associated with the nation's construction and defense has affirmed that the strength of the entire people's national defense and the power of the people's war to defend the Fatherland is the combined strength due to many the constituent factors, in which, economy is one of the factors that play a dominant and decisive role in the development of national defense to serve the war to protect the country. Therefore, the issue of economic construction, building the material and technical foundations of socialism to develop production, gradually improving people's lives, building potentials for national defense makes it especially important.

Economic construction and development make all workers live in independence, freedom, prosperity and happiness, making each citizen deeply attached to the new social regime, with a will to fight high, have the necessary material means to protect the Fatherland and defend the regime. The Army's goals of participation in labor production, construction of economic development are increasing the Army's strength and the nation's general strength; contribute to building an independent and autonomous economy, including defense economy. It is doing good economics and also doing good defense. “In the process of economic construction, it is necessary to closely combine economy with defense, defense and economy, ensuring that the two tasks of economic building and defense consolidation are carried out reasonably, making every step of economic development has the effect of enhancing the strength of national defense and each step of defense development enhances the ability to build and protect the economy and protect the country” [4].

From the situation and the task of building a whole population national defense, building the people's armed forces in our country in the current revolutionary period, the Politburo's Resolution (March 1976) on the issue of the military. The economic mission has affirmed: “Being ready to fight and to fight well is the common mission, the most important strategic mission of the entire army. Building the Army astute, strong, effective, ready to serve and successfully complete all missions both in peacetime and wartime, especially in modern warfare. At the same time, labor for production, economic construction, national construction was a common task, a very important strategic task of the whole army”. Therefore, in order to encourage the entire people to join the armed forces, the Party based on the revolutionary situation and tasks in each period to set an appropriate mobilization regime, from the voluntary enlistment regime to the by-law military service. This is a new development in the drafting of the implementation of the entire people's armed forces, the entire people's militarization and the building of the people's army.

In the process of building a regular and modern army, the Party has paid attention to directing the implementation of necessary military reforms, especially the reform of the army from volunteering to the military service regime. The, aimed at building a strong standing army and a strong reserve army, significantly reducing military spending to serve the construction of the country's economy. The People's Army of Vietnam when it was first established was an army built on a volunteer regime. The first guerrilla teams formed in the resistance war consisted of soldiers volunteering to save the country and protect national independence. During the anti-French resistance war, although the government set out military service to mobilize the maximum military force, in reality, the voluntary regime was still actively participated by the people. When the North was liberated, the state government was strongly consolidated, the revolutionary army conditionally advanced to military service. Implementing the military service regime has the effect of raising the awareness of every citizen for the defense mission, preparing all citizens to participate in the cause of national defense.

When peace is restored, the Party and Government have proposed a policy of transferring a part of active soldiers to the production front to increase forces for economic recovery, national construction, and combine the requirements of the task of

Inheritance and Bring Into Play “Ngu Binh U Nong” In Strengthening the People Armed Force Intergrated the Current Economic Development with National Defense

economic building, reducing the number of troops, increasing the production force with the requirement of defense consolidation is to focus on training new classes of soldiers, strengthening the militia and self-defense force, organizing The backward force is strong to protect the Fatherland, protect peace. The process of industrialization and modernization of the country is both an economic task and a defense one, because if we want to have modern defense, we must have modern industry. Building modern agriculture is about doing business but also doing national defense, because "real wealth, military power", food is always a huge strategic issue in both peacetime and wartime.

Building a modern transportation system is economic but also defense, because modern war requires the army to be very mobile. There is a new economic concentration that can enhance national defense potential and improve defense capabilities. Therefore, economic construction is the content of defense consolidation. In peaceful conditions of national construction, enthusiastic production, economic development, and national construction are concentrated expressions of patriotism and sense of national defense of each people [5].

Relying on the patriotism and love for socialism of the entire people, on the already enacted military service regime, the Party successfully led "wartime reinforcement work, rapidly expanding the armed forces. People on the basis of a strong force organized and ready from peacetime ... a large number of elite young people, from rural to urban areas, in cooperatives and factories, offices, schools ... have risen. Way to battle, joining army units, youth volunteers, fighting bravely, working selflessly on battlefields, setting up brilliant victories, great achievements" [6].

Based on agriculture production activities and economic construction, the Army has made important contributions to the re-adjustment of forces across regions and regions, in accordance with the strategy of national defense, socio-economic development, and so the defense and security posture would be firmly established in strategic areas, protecting the Fatherland from early and from a distance threats. Several lessons learned in building forces to ensure defense and security posture in the current period that are: firstly, well uptake the Party's point of view on the relationship between economic growth and national defense so that each step of economic development is a step in enhancing defense potential and expanding foreign relations. second, based on specific requirements on economic development, choosing how to effectively combine economy with defense, between economic development and national construction and defense in the context of international integration. Third, the military must become the core force to combine economy with defense. Fourth, the combination of economy and defense must lay the nation interests in priority, considering this as the ultimate principle of all economic and defense activities.

IV. CONCLUSION

The “Ngu binh u nong” policy was continuously issued by the Ly - Tran - Le prim dynasties, beginning in the Ly Dynasty (XI - XII centuries), continuing in the Tran dynasty (XIII - XIV centuries), and culminating in the early Le dynasty (15th century). This strategy is the plan to establish an armed force to maintain the country within the people, related with production, closely connecting "army" with "agricultural", economics and defense in a purpose of struggle in the growth of national history. This strategy also leaves significant lessons that have been inherited in our country's socialist revolution today, aimed at the job of developing the people's armed forces, laying the groundwork for strong national defense.

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